

ON THE SIGNIFICANCE OF QUALIMETRIC METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE LEADERSHIP PERFORMANCE OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL PRINCIPALS

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada ta'lim muassasalari rahbarlarining boshqaruv faoliyati sifatini baholashda kvalimetrik yondashuvning nazariy asoslari tahlil qilinadi. Bu yondashuv ta'lim tashkilotlari rahbarlarining boshqaruv faoliyati sifatini baholashda asosiy mezonlarni aniqlash va ularni kompleks tarzda inobatga olishga qaratilgan. Ishda boshqaruv sifatini aniqlashning turli usullari ko'rib chiqiladi, rahbarlarni baholashning kompleks mezonlari tizimi tasvirlanadi, shuningdek, boshqaruv faoliyati sifatini baholashga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy prinsiplar, omillar va qo'llash imkoniyatlari yoritib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Umumiy o'rta ta'lim, maktab direktori, kvalimetrik yondashuv, boshqaruv faoliyati, faoliyatni baholash, kvalimetriya, boshqaruv mezonlari, kasbiy rivojlanish, o'lchov usullari.

Аннотации: В статье проводится анализ теоретических основ квалиметрического подхода к оценке качества управленческой деятельности руководителей образовательных учреждений. Этот подход направлен на определение основных критериев оценки качества управленческой деятельности руководителей образовательных организаций и комплексное их учёт. В работе рассматриваются различные методы определения качества управления, описывается система комплексных критериев оценки руководителей, а также освещаются основные принципы, факторы и возможности применения, влияющие на оценку качества управленческой деятельности.

Ключевые слова: Общее среднее образование, директор школы, квалиметрический подход, управленческая деятельность, ценка деятельности, квалиметрия, критерии управления, профессиональное развитие, методы измерения.

Annotation: The article analyzes the theoretical foundations of the qualimetric approach to evaluating the quality of management activities of heads of educational institutions. This approach is aimed at identifying the main criteria for assessing the quality of management activities of educational organization leaders and considering them comprehensively. The study examines various methods for determining management quality, describes a system of complex criteria for evaluating leaders, and also highlights the key principles, factors, and application possibilities that influence the assessment of management activity quality.

Keywords: General secondary education, school principal, qualimetric approach, management activity, performance evaluation, qualimetry, management criteria, professional development, measurement methods.

General secondary school principals are responsible for the successful organization and management of the educational process. Qualimetric approaches play a crucial role in evaluating their managerial activities, as these approaches help identify and assess the

competencies of principals. This article analyzes the essence of the qualimetric approach in evaluating the managerial activities of general secondary school directors and its application in practice.

At present, the effective management of an educational institution is a matter of particular importance, which can be explained by three factors. First, depending on the competent actions of the management hierarchy, human resources can be used efficiently, teachers' labor productivity can be increased, and local and regional socio-cultural, economic and other issues can be addressed. Second, the professional development level and personal qualities of leaders do not always fully conform to the requirements of normative-legal documents. Third, there is an increasing need for a clear and well-substantiated selection process when appointing heads of educational institutions.

In evaluating the quality of managerial activities of general secondary school principals, approaches such as staged, structural-functional, client-oriented, integrative, process-oriented, and results-oriented methods are widely used. However, we have adopted the qualimetric concept as our foundation, which is based on the conceptual foundations of pedagogical measurement theory, the prevalence and independence of expert evaluation processes, and the methods of mathematical statistics and pedagogical analysis.

This approach enables the provision of information about the level of preparedness and the degree of professional-personal development of educational institution leaders in a clear, orderly, and sufficiently objective manner, and on that basis allows the identification and justification of the factors, functions, principles, criteria, and indicators for its implementation [1].

In scientific literature, the theoretical and methodological foundations for assessing educational quality within the framework of qualimetric methods have been extensively developed, based on the synthesis of the theory of general functional systems, as well as resource-dependence, process-oriented, and modular principles. In the research, the effectiveness of a didactic system for ensuring the quality of professional training has been theoretically validated, and a criterion-based assessment apparatus has been developed.

Moreover, numerous researchers are conducting in-depth studies of the features of the qualimetric approach to evaluating the quality of training for different actors in educational relationships. The qualimetric approach is a systematic method used to measure and assess managerial performance. It assists in identifying the parameters needed to analyze, evaluate, and develop leaders' competencies. The qualimetric approach comprises the following core elements:

Evaluation Criteria: It is necessary to establish clear criteria for assessing the performance of leaders. These criteria should include the leader's management competencies, ability to make quality decisions, and skills in managing and developing the team.

Measurement Methods: In a qualimetric approach, measurement methods play a crucial role. The measurements must provide clear and objective results when evaluating the performance of leaders. These methods are implemented through surveys, interviews, experiments, and observations.

Analysis of Results: The obtained results are analyzed to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the leaders. This process helps determine directions for the development of leadership skills.

Advantages of the Qualimetric Approach for General Secondary School Principals:

1. **Objective Evaluation:** The qualimetric approach allows for an objective assessment of the leaders' performance. This helps leaders adapt to changes and develop their competencies.

2. **Development of Strategic Plans:** Based on the obtained results, development strategies can be created for school leaders. These strategies aim to strengthen their weaknesses and further enhance their strengths.

3. **Improvement of the Educational Environment:** Through the qualimetric approach, leaders gain the opportunity to take measures aimed at improving the educational environment within their teams. This, in turn, enhances the quality of the educational process.

Among the various types and approaches to selecting candidates for leadership positions and evaluating their performance (formal, a posteriori, heuristic), the following psychometric approaches, based on the use of tools for assessing the competencies of educational leaders, are the most popular:

1. **Conducting the Talent Q Test** – This is a personnel assessment process aimed at identifying the potential of employees. As a result, the gap between the employee's actual level of applied competencies and the required level specified in the organization's competency profile for the given position is identified [5].

2. **20-Dimensional Personal Questionnaire** - This tool enables a comprehensive assessment of managerial staff's personal and professional qualities, as well as their behavior in various work situations.

In this case, the leader's 20 core competencies are conditionally divided into five groups:

- Managerial Skills (leadership, developing subordinates, staff management, planning and organizing);

- Motivation (personal development, result orientation, attention to quality, initiative);

- Decision-Making Skills (systemic thinking, commercial and economic thinking, data collection, problem analysis);

- Personal Characteristics (positive thinking, responsibility, stress resistance, adaptability);

- Interpersonal Skills (interpersonal understanding, teamwork, effective communication, relationship building).

A distinctive feature of this tool is the flexibility of its mathematical algorithm. By combining different scales, it becomes possible to accurately assess virtually any competency [2].

3. **SAPPHIRE Strategy** – This strategy allows for the analysis of a person's ability to quickly and accurately assess complex information from various sources, as well as to draw conclusions regarding market development trends, the prospects of large-scale projects, and business opportunities [4].

As the next type of evaluation of management quality in the education sector, competitive examinations and participation of leaders in the following activities can be considered:

- Selection of reserve personnel for management positions;

- Evaluation of competencies, professional qualities, and personal traits of leaders during competitions such as "Best School Principal of the Year," "Best Innovative School Principal of the Year," and "Best Young School Principal of the Year";

Participation in project schools, case championships, creative sessions, foresight sessions, strategic sessions, and business games (for example, the “Future League”, which is aimed at solving social problems and creating additional opportunities for youth career development).

These competitive processes are used to obtain comprehensive and objective information about the level of managerial skills, determine management effectiveness, establish regional and federal ratings, verify compliance with the basic professional training level of graduates, adequately assess the competencies formed in leaders, identify gaps, increase qualification levels, and develop both general and professional culture of the leaders.

The above-mentioned approaches and technologies for evaluating the quality of managerial activity are generally non-systematic and based on selective participation. However, they are considered universal and can be applied to assess a wide range of managers, as currently, there are no specific mathematical methods developed for evaluating the performance of heads of educational institutions such as kindergartens, schools, technical colleges, and other types of educational organizations.

Based on a comparative analysis of pedagogical literature, the key aspects for developing a qualimetric approach have been formulated.

The theoretical model for assessing the quality of managerial activity is based on the following components:

- Problems (identification of key shortcomings);
- Functional (reliance on the functions of the leader);
- Environment (consideration of current conditions and influencing factors).

The analysis of literature on educational management issues shows that one of the most relevant and effective approaches is the environment-oriented approach, which involves assessing the leader's ability and skills to adapt their managerial activity to time, labor market conditions, societal demands, and employer expectations.

This approach considers the following key conditions:

- Collaborative (expanding cooperation with potential employers);
- Socio-economic (increased competition in the modern labor market);
- Regulatory-legal (ensuring that leadership activities operate within the legal framework);
- Subjective-determined (professional and personal needs and expectations of management staff in the education system, their aspiration for professional and personal growth), and others [3].

To meet the objective demands of society, a modern school principal must develop the following professional competencies and personal qualities:

K1 – Pedagogical Culture: A thorough understanding of educational content and methods, the ability to comprehend students' developmental processes and preparedness, and understanding of andragogical principles [5];

K2 – Commercial Thinking: The ability to make decisions considering commercial interests, assess situations from the perspective of cost-effectiveness, and take into account the organization's strategic goals;

K3 – Motivation: Initiative and result orientation, including taking additional actions beyond assigned responsibilities to proactively influence situations;

K4 – Leadership: Personal responsibility for the outcomes of the pedagogical team, defining the educational institution's tasks, coordinating and aligning efforts to implement

them, fostering a developmental and motivational environment within the team, and providing support, encouragement, and recognition;

K5 – Decision-Making Ability, including in emergency situations;

K6 – Resilience: Positive expectations regarding personal growth and development, self-confidence, psychological adaptability and flexibility, organizational capacity, perseverance in achieving set goals, positive emotions, and coping strategies for managing or overcoming stress, as well as the ability to deal with fear, procrastination, and betrayal;

K7 – Effective Communication: The ability to express thoughts clearly and logically, present persuasive arguments when addressing opposing viewpoints, and defend personal opinions.

When combined, these competencies—taking into account the high importance of pedagogical culture and commercial thinking for school leaders, along with the significance of educational background and work experience—form the basis of a qualimetric model for evaluating leadership performance quality:

$$E_r = \frac{(2K_1 + 2K_2 + 2K_3 + K_4 + K_5 + K_6 + K_7 + K_o)}{8} \times 100\%$$

Where:

E_r – Leader's effectiveness;

K – Competency;

2 – Weighting coefficient;

K_o – Work experience and educational background.

According to the number of points scored by the leader, the following performance levels are proposed, reflecting their readiness to fulfill managerial functions:

80% to 100% – Transformational Level: Demonstrates openness to new trends and opportunities, a strong drive for innovation, implementation of bold reforms, generation of innovative solutions, inspiration from new experiences in various fields, and a high degree of creativity;

60% to 79% – Systematic Level: Capable of establishing organizational work systems, focused on consistent and step-by-step implementation of educational projects and programs;

Below 59% – Adaptive Level: Shows readiness to effectively adapt in uncertain conditions, respond to changes, seek new experiences, embrace alternative perspectives, and synthesize ideas.

Thus, there is a growing trend toward improving educational management and ensuring objective and accurate evaluation of managerial staff. This sets new tasks for school leaders such as developing professionally, defining effective cooperation standards, clarifying professional competencies, and integrating innovative technologies.

As part of our research outlook, we aim to develop several relevant directions that consider current requirements and conditions. These include exploring innovative working styles of school leaders, addressing issues of digitalization and transformation in education, and strengthening the educational component in teaching. In our view, this will lead to changes in professional behavior and improvements in the preparation level of school leaders.

In conclusion, the application of the qualimetric approach in evaluating the managerial performance of general secondary school principals helps to identify and develop their competencies. This approach contributes to improving the management of educational

institutions, ensuring the professional growth of leaders, and enhancing the overall quality of education. The practical implementation of the qualimetric approach can lead to positive changes in the general secondary education system.

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